

Green hydrogen production whit offshore wind at Colombian Caribbean Sea: Analysis for Atlántico Department's coasts

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Authors contribution

All authors contributed to the: study conception and design, data collection, analysis and interpretation of results, draft manuscript preparation. For the draft manuscript, redaction was leaded as indicated: introduction and wind farm location selection (Andres Rincon), requirements and typology selection (Julian Berrio), technical parameters estimation (Jose Llain), economical assessment and conclusions (Edwin Bermejo).

Introduction

Hydrogen is an energy array opportunity for worldwide energy decarbonization. Actual production is limited and mostly produced by fossil fuels, then it is required to increase its production by clean energy sources. In Colombia, actual hydrogen is around 150 kton (produced principally from reformed natural gas) [1]. Green hydrogen demand is expected to increase to 790 kton to 2040. Then exist a need for Colombia to explore massive green hydrogen productions. Colombian has different clean energy potentials, on of them is the offshore wind production that have not been exploited.

For the use of offshore wind to hydrogen production there are different technical aspects to be considered. The electrolyzer technologies, water requirements, wind turbine offshore platforms and energy transmission vector are briefly discussed to contextualize state of technology for the project.

Electrolysis is the method used to separate hydrogen and oxygen by applying an electrical current. In the Table 1 main electrolyzer technologies are compared.

Table 1. Comparative of key industrial green hydrogen production technologies.

Technology	Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE)	Alkaline Electrolysis (AEL)	Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysis (PEMEL)
Main characteristic	High-temperature (~ 700 °C) electrolysis technology.	Use a liquid electrolyte.	It has the highest TRL (7-8) when it comes to coupling with a dynamic electric input. [2]
Highest efficiency up to 2019	≥ 79 %	~ 70 %	~ 60 %
Advantages	High efficiency.	Cost-effective solution.	Shorter start-up times.
Challenges for offshore applications	High temperatures challenge material stability. Leakage could increase, thus probable fire event.	Liquid electrolyte increase the likelihood of leakage and maintenance requirements.	Use expensive catalysts (e.g. platinum/iridium).

For electrolyzers connected to only one wind turbine, it would receive discontinues electricity. The time response for AEL and PEMEL ranges from 1 s to 1 min. From short to mid-term applications AEL and PEMEL seems to be the most promising electrolysis technologies.

For these technologies, water used for electrolysis must be high purity (≤ 0.5 ppm total dissolved units). Fresh water is required for hydrogen production in a proportion of $\sim 9 L_{H_2O}/kg_{H_2}$. Thus, freshwater access is an issue for FOW hydrogen production [2].

Sea water can cause corrosive damage and lead to chlorine production, decreasing life expectancy from the technology. While saline water electrolysis technologies are researched, seawater desalination must be conducted prior to described electrolyzer technologies.

Reverse Osmosis technology has already been used for PEMEL without a significant reduction in performance. It can be adapted to different flowrates and operate autonomously. The desalination unit typically requires seawater pumping (energy consumption varies from $2 - 4 kWh/m^3$) [3]. For the proposed facility, the energy is taken from the turbine. Thus, desalination operation only increases costs for up to $0.018 \text{ €/}kg_{H_2}$ [4].

Desalination also must be considered in the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) for the Environmental License of the project. Brine and other discharge desalination subproducts must be analyzed for proper disposal. Also, environmental monitoring plans should be developed.

On the other hands turbines can be fixed for water depths less than 70 m, or requires floating platforms for deeper waters. Semi-submersible, spar, barge, tension-leg platform are the key types of floating platforms (Figure 1). In economic terms, the more viable options are semi-submersible and spar platforms [5].

Figure 1. Floating offshore wind platforms [2].

For the IEA Wind 15 MW turbine exists a conceptual spar floater (called “WindGrete”) [6] designed by the EU Horizon 2020 project COREWIND. There has no been reported semi-submersible floaters design for it.

For the INNWIND 10 MW turbine exists an open access semi-submersible three leg floater designed by CENER . For alternatives where the electrolysis facility required to be installed on deck of wind turbine, barge and semi-submersible designs are preferred for its deck’s area available [2]. Thus, alternatives with integrated electrolysis facilities can consider the INNWIND 10 MW turbine with the INNWIND semi-submersible open access design, and options that does not required such integration can consider the IEA Wind 15 MW with the WindGrete spar design.

Figure 2. Offshore fixed foundations. Adapted from [7].

Figure 2 presents the options for fixed offshore foundations for wind turbines. Fixed offshore foundations are typically less expensive than the floating platforms and commonly used for different turbine sizes.

The energy from the offshore wind hydrogen production can be transmitted directly in electric power transmission from the turbine or with the hydrogen as an energy vector through pipelines. Its main classification can be observed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Main energy transmission vectors classification for an FOW hydrogen production farm. PENDING REFERENCE PER IMAGE

For distances greater than 60 km subsea or 200 km oversea HVDC cables performs better economically than the HVAC cables [8]. In the HVDC links, Voltage Source Converters (VSC) are preferred over Line Commutated Converters (LCC) because it has a grid-independent end unit and less required projected horizontal area (about half of an LCC technology). Dynamic cables are 30% - 50% more expensive than static cables (of the same capacity) for voltages rated up to 33 kV. This is even higher (60% - 90%) in 66 kV cables [9].

On the other hand, transportation efficient of hydrogen in pipelines is usually compared to that of natural gas. Transportation efficiency may be correlated with pressure drop because of distance travelled and further depends on the thermal energy of the substance transported.

Submarine static hydrogen pipelines are not commercially yet mature. Submarine natural gas pipelines exists and through physical correlations, scaling to hydrogen applications can be estimated [2]. As an example a study conducted to assess new offshore hydrogen pipelines in the North Sea found that to reach hydrogen with a pressure of 68 bar, then 86 bar pressure input is required. Required diameter vary from 0.25 m – 0.30 m for 1 GW installed capacity (in distances less than 180 km) to ~0.57 m for 5 GW capacity over the same range of distances [10].

Flexible pipelines are composed of different layers. Each one accomplishes different functions for the pipeline (i.e. corrosion protection, insulation, pressure containment, hydrogen containment) [11]. Flexible pipelines generally range internal diameter 0.05 m – 0.5 m.

Finally, for the Alkaline electrolysis technologies compression system is required because of max 30 bar pressure output from this kind of technologies [2]. Due to hydrogen low molecular weight centrifugal compressors are not recommended, then reciprocated compressors are recommended for hydrogen applications with pressures required over 30 bar.

This project aims to assess technical and economic aspects of green hydrogen production with offshore wind at Atlántico Department from Colombia. Initially it is selected the wind farm location according to commercial and environmental aspects, then project requirements are identified according to Colombia's law framework. Technical assessment is developed for the selected alternative for green hydrogen production with offshore wind. And finally, economical assessment and conclusions are presented.

Wind farm location selection

Atlántico Department's coasts are located 10.8° - 11.5° N. Due to its equatorial closeness, it is part of (or close to) the Intertropical Convergence Zone and wind is more usual to come from the north-east direction (Figure 4). Offshore winds are typically IEC class I or II.

Figure 4. a) Intertropical Convergence Zone precipitation and atmospheric moist static energy flux [12]. b) Wind rose of Atlántico Department's coast [13].

Offshore have different current usages at Colombia Caribbean shores. It is used commercially for fishing, shipping, and tourism. There are also preserved regions by its biodiversity. The Offshore Wind Roadmap for Colombia [14] evaluated commercial usages, environmental and technical aspects for offshore wind projects to take into account. Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7 summarize main aspects considered in the Offshore Wind Roadmap.

Figure 5. Technical aspects for offshore wind projects at Colombian Caribbean Sea. a) Bathymetric map. b) Offshore wind speeds. Adapted from [14].

Bathymetric map (Figure 5. a) indicates that water depths less than 70 m are suitable for bottom fixed foundations solutions. Mean wind speed is higher for areas far away from the shore (Figure 5. b). Fixed bottom regions have mean wind speeds from 7 m/s – 10 m/s. Offshore floating regions (depths from 70 m to 1250 m) presents typical mean wind speeds from 8 m/s to higher than 10 m/s. For fixed bottom region the highest mean wind speeds are at *Bocas de Cenizas* (Rio Magdalena’s river mouth), but that is a region used for commerce in Barranquilla.

Figure 6. Commercial aspects for offshore wind projects at Colombian Caribbean Sea. a) Shipping constraints. b) Commercial and artisanal fishing. Adapted from [14].

Figure 6. a) presents the ship density travels from 2015 to 2020. Colombian Caribbean Sea shipping is represented mainly at Barranquilla, Cartagena, and Santa Marta ports with 5.2, 2.7 and 7.2 million TEU respectively in 2018 [15]. Also, industrial fishing occurs at regions far away from shore (Figure 6. b). Wind farm must not be located at high density shipping areas neither industrial fishing areas (unless

the economic benefits are greater than the commerce). Thus, it is recommended to explore bottom fixed solutions closer to the shore.

Figure 7. Environmental relevant areas to consider for offshore wind projects at Colombian Caribbean Sea [14].

Close to Atlántico’s shore there are few priority conservation sites and some marine important sites (Figure 7). Thus, the Renewables Consultant Group identified the 14 initial exploration areas for wind offshore presented in Figure 8. a.

Figure 8. a) Wind offshore initial exploration areas [14]. b) Selected wind farm location at Atlántico Department's coasts. Adapted from [13].

The proposed wind farm in this project attempts to local hydrogen demand. Then FX-1 area has been selected for the wind farm location. In Figure 8.b, the specific area for projects calculations is presented. It is close to Santa Verónica's coasts from Atlántico Department.

Even though this area has less restrictions according to commercial and current environmental restrictions, further studies and proper licensing is required for this kind of projects approval. In the next section, the main typical requirements are explained.

Requirements [Julian Berrio]

For the project it is necessary to consider different aspects which are a key part of the system of production of electric energy and hydrogen, these can be mandatory requirements or key considerations from which to start the development of the project, these are:

1. Studies and approvals

The projects require authorizations from the relevant authorities and the studies requested by them. The following is a list of the authorizations and studies that would be required for an offshore wind farm in Barranquilla.

According to Decree 1076 of 2015, the *Autoridad Nacional de Licencias Ambientales* (National Environmental Licensing Authority), or the *Corporación Autónoma regional o de Desarrollo Sostenible* (regional Autonomous or Sustainable Development Corporation), or the district or metropolitan area (for populations greater than 1 million inhabitants within its urban perimeter) are competent entities for the issuance of the environmental license. The following studies must be included:

- Environmental Diagnosis of Alternatives.
- Environmental Impact Study .

Also, due to the nature of the project it is recommended to consider:

- Oceanographic and bathymetric study.
- Fauna and flora impact study.
- Noise and vibration study.
- Visual impact study.

- Project location study

Initially it is required to identify the potential areas of the municipality where the project could be carried out; considering within the selection criteria: wind potential of the area, current use of the area, ecosystems and biodiversity present.

- Studies about wind information in the selected area

The wind potential of the area needs to be investigated with more precise measurements than those of the project location study. In case there is not enough technical or academic information, wind measurements are required for the design of the wind farm.

Also to be considered are resolutions such as Resolution number (0240-2021) MD-DIMAR-SUBDEMAR-ALIT of March 26, 2021, which establishes "Protection of the Marine Environment and

Coastal Areas coastal environment", concerning the establishment of criteria and procedures for the temporary installation of data temporary installation of data collection infrastructure in maritime waters, maritime beaches and/or low-tide land under maritime waters, maritime beaches and/or low tide lands under the jurisdiction of Dimar".

2. Structures

For the development of a project is necessary the use of structures which ensure the proper functioning of the entire system, these are intended to cover needs and functions within the project, either the generation of electricity such as wind turbines or the production of hydrogen from structures where the electrolysis process is carried out and its storage and transportation, in this section the structural requirements of the project are specified.

- **Foundations**

Foundations play a key role in securing wind turbine and tower structures to the seabed. These structures, usually made of steel, are inserted into the various layers of the seabed. The specific choice of foundation type is influenced by multiple factors, including seabed characteristics such as soil type and properties, water depth, wave and wind forces, as well as the likelihood of extreme weather events. Also considered is the capacity required to withstand the dynamic forces of the wind turbine itself. [1]

- **Subsea cables and interconnection:**

Beyond the foundations, the plant consists of essential infrastructure to convert turbine energy into usable form. It includes three key offshore components:

- Interconnection cables that connect the turbines to an offshore substation.
- The offshore substation, which elevates the power for export.
- A high-voltage cable that transmits the power from the offshore substation to the onshore grid.

Developers and EPC companies must comply with current DIMAR regulations for submarine cables. The Electricity Law (Law 143 of 1994) establishes the rules for the generation, transmission, interconnection, distribution, and commercialization of electric power.

- **Energy storage:**

Wind speed varies constantly throughout the day, making it impossible to maintain constant power generation. As a result, hydrogen production through the electrolyzers also becomes variable. To ensure constant hydrogen production throughout the day, it is necessary to implement a battery bank. This bank stores the energy peaks generated by the wind turbines and supplies them to the electrolyzers at times when the wind speed is not sufficient to maintain a constant power output. In this way, stable hydrogen production is guaranteed throughout the day.

- ***Electrolysis facility***

A plant where the electrolysis process is carried out is a fundamental structure in this project, for it must comply with the protection of both the electrolysis equipment or the operating personnel of the same, according to the chosen typology (see in the typology section) this must be located on land next to the electrical substation of land.

- ***Hydrogen storage***

The most common and technologically mature form of storage is as compressed gas. The gas is confined under high pressure in cylinders made of different materials. Depending on the material of which the container is constructed, the gas storage pressure varies. Composite materials are now used for tank construction (polymers, fibers, resins), with the aim of increasing the pressure and reducing the size of the container for the same amount of gas. Hydrogen tanks have to be specially prepared to withstand high pressures and fatigue due to continuous loading and unloading cycles [16].

3. Hydrogen

- ***Electrolizer***

Electrolysis is the key process in the production of hydrogen, it is here where water is separated into its constituent molecules [17], and the choice of the type of technology to use for this process depends on several factors depending on the location of the electrolyzer, onshore or offshore, it is for this reason that according to the selected project location, the most convenient type of hydrogen production, taking into account the proximity of the turbines to the coast, is the Centralized onshore electrolysis, where the weight of the electrolyzer has no influence since it must be located on land and fed by a wind turbine farm by means of submarine cables. In this typology an electrical substation is required both onshore and offshore as part of the wind farm design. The purpose of this onshore substation would be to lower the voltage of the received electricity to operate the onshore electrolyzer [2].

According to the above information the electrolysis technology profile that fits this typology is alkaline electrolysis due to its cost effectiveness compared to other technologies as well as offering competitive system efficiency.

- ***Desalinizer***

Water electrolysis requires high purity water, either directly in membrane electrolyzers or in a mixture with salts for alkaline water electrolyzers. Water purity should have a maximum of 0.5 ppm total dissolved units (TDS). Around 9 L of water are needed to produce 1 kg of hydrogen. In onshore environments, this is relatively easy to secure from mains water supply. It can be provided by incorporating water purification systems into the electrolyser system or via external pre-treatment [2].

4. Business model

The commercialization of the hydrogen and/or energy generated by the project is important for its financial sustainability. The following is a list of the key aspects to be defined for this purpose:

- **Target market**

The target market and the applications where there is an opportunity must be identified. It is known to have a place in the chemical industry, mobility (hydrogen vehicles), energy production, steel production and other industrial processes.

- **Customer needs**

It must be clear about the specific needs of customers in each sector and adapt to make inroads with hydrogen to meet those needs.

- **Business model and pricing**

Pricing strategies and the model for marketing hydrogen throughout the supply chain to the end consumer must be defined. It is important to select distributors with the capacity to store and transport and to generate corporate agreements.

- **To educate about the use of green hydrogen.**

There is a need to generate a culture of benefits and applications

- **Marketing**

A mechanism should be created to promote green hydrogen through marketing campaigns aimed at industry and strategic customers.

- **Innovation**

An item should be allocated for research and development to generate advances and the use of new technologies and market trends to maintain a competitive advantage.

5. Others

- **Emergency systems**

Priority to the implementation of robust emergency systems. These systems are designed to address a variety of unforeseen situations. Detailed protocols will be established and specialized devices will be installed to ensure effective and rapid responses to potential contingencies.

The following outline shows in simplified form the key requirements for this project

Fig.#. Scheme of requirements

Typology selection [Julian B]

The offshore distance and the capacity of the farm are key-drivers for the suitable transport methodology. The two main solutions have either electrolysis performed onshore with submarine electric cables as the energy transmission vector, or have electrolysis performed offshore with hydrogen pipelines as the energy transmission vector. [2].

1. Centralised onshore electrolysis

A green hydrogen production plant running on an offshore wind facility, by means of a conventional grid connection can be normally built onshore where: (i) land is cheap; and (ii) there are no major health and safety implications or critical nearby infrastructure; and (iii) the capacity of the electricity grid is sufficient for the level of hydrogen proposed, taking electricity from a floating offshore wind farm in water with significant depth. The FOW output is sent to shore using submarine electric cables where it is then converted to hydrogen, which goes through the rest of the supply chain for storage and distribution [2]. As shown in Figure 9

Figure 9 Onshore electrolysis system typology layout using spar platform, dynamic electric cabling, and both an offshore and onshore substation. [1].

2. Decentralised offshore electrolysis.

In this typology, hydrogen is produced offshore by the farm then exported in hydrogen pipelines to the shore for storage and distribution. In a current day wind turbine, the electrical power is first generated in AC. In a first stage, it is converted into DC initially to flatten the frequency. In a second stage, it is converted back to AC so that it can be fed into the array cables with a 50 Hz. Onshore electrolysis system typology layout using spar platform, dynamic electric cabling, and both an offshore and onshore substation. Renewable and Sustainable. The electrolyser is located on the turbine platform, avoiding any type of electrical power transmission. This would avoid the use of converters, leading to energy and cost savings. The decentralised term comes from conducting electrolysis in a decentralised configuration on the floating deck of individual turbines [2]. As shown in Figure 10

Figure 10 Decentralised offshore electrolysis typology layout using a semi-submersible platform with a flexible pipe connected to static submarine pipelines. [1].

3. Centralised offshore electrolysis.

This typology is close to the centralised onshore one but with the electrolysis facility installed offshore. Produced hydrogen is sent to the shore in hydrogen pipelines, and these are the only energy transmission vector considered. This configuration offers easier and quicker maintenance access for individual turbines, and generally a less complex system than the decentralised one. The offshore electrolysis facility is installed in a centralised configuration on a floating vessel. Similar to the decentralised typology, it is comprised of the electrolyzers, cooling units, seawater desalination units, hydrogen buffer, and a battery system for back-up power to the facility. [2]. As shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Centralised offshore electrolysis typology layout using a spar platform with a floating vessel accommodating the electrolysis facility. [1].

According to the above information, selection of the project location Figure 12 and the target demand, which is national, in addition to thinking of a relatively low cost system which meets the objectives of the project in the long term, it can be concluded that the most appropriate typology is Centralised onshore electrolysis, since it fits the proximity of the project to the coast and represents fewer limitations compared to an electrolysis system located in the sea, which is why this typology allows an electrolyzer with more capacity and a treatment plant with a more efficient maintenance and access. some advantages and disadvantages of this typology are shown in the diagram in Figure 13.

Figure 12 Location and distribution of the project.

Figure 13 Advantages and disadvantages of Centralised onshore electrolysis. [2]

Technical parameters estimation JOSE

The estimation of technical parameters in a wind farm for green hydrogen production is crucial to achieve the goals set forth in the project. The demand for green hydrogen by 2040 is projected to reach 790kt from low-emission sources, while the aim of this project is to meet the current demand

(in 2023) of 150kt, with most of it coming from blue and grey hydrogen. This figure would represent 19% of the 2040 demand.

Figure 14 illustrates the methodology used to calculate the number of turbines required for the wind farm."

Figure 14 Methodology of Wind potential

For calculate the wind potential, we collect the data of the wind speed during the year at 100m (Figure 15), this information is available at global wind atlas, The Figure 15 shows a significant variability in wind speed, with an increase towards the end of the year and the beginning of the year. This is because the Caribbean coast is in a season of trade winds, and these trade winds intensify and increase in speed.

Figure 15 Wind speed during the year at 100m

With this curve, we calculate the annual wind speed at hub height (150m), this was 9,03m/s. After that, in the curve of annual energy production of turbine Vesta V236-15,00MW

ANNUAL ENERGY PRODUCTION

Figure 16 ANNUAL ENERGY PRODUCTION, VESTAS V236-15,00MW

This result of the curve of annual energy production (Figure 16) means a power of turbine during the year is 8MW, recalculating the capacity factor is now 0.53, higher than we estimate before (0.5) this means that the project accomplishes the goal of produce 150kt of green hydrogen per year.

Wind farm effects

The effects of a wind farm represent a very important parameter to consider; some of these are.

- The turbine reduces wind speed in downwind areas.
- The relative location of the wind and rotor causes the wake to change its orientation relative to the turbine frame.
- This affects the total resulting power of the wind farm.

The Figure 17 shows the power of the wind farm when the wind direction is changing, in this case when the wind directions are in North – West (311° and 349°) and South- East (131° and 169°), the power of the wind farm is maximum. On the other hand, yaw control can help optimize the power of the wind farm when the wind speed keeps changing, turning the direction of the blades to the optimal.

Figure 17 Power of wind farm

Economical assessment

EDWIN

To produce green hydrogen with a wind energy source, it is necessary to evaluate the economic and financial viability of the project.

In this analysis the following elements are considered:

- **Initial investment cost:**

The acquisition costs of wind turbines, electrolysis equipment, supporting infrastructure, storage systems, substations, wiring and other supplies. License costs are also included here.

In a Deep Resource post [1], we found an important estimate of the cost of a turbine, based on extrapolation of the \$12.3 MUSD cost of a 14MW turbine published by Rystad Energy. Extrapolating to our case, the cost of the 15MW turbine is \$13.2 MUSD. An estimate is also made for the cost of the foundation between \$3-4 million and the cost of \$12 MUSD in cabling for lengths of 50 km offshore and 15 km onshore, an installation cost of \$2 MUSD. With this guide we estimate the unit costs shown in the table1.

- **Operation and maintenance cost:**

Annual operation and maintenance costs of wind turbines, electrolysis systems, electrical substations, hydrogen storage and auxiliary equipment. The costs of personnel, repairs, insurance, and other expenses related to the operation of the project are considered.

Our guide to determining maintenance costs is based on the Weather Guard Lightning Tech publication, Wind Turbine Cost: How Much? [1]. The average cost is estimated at \$48 TUSD per year.

- **Production costs and sales income:**

Costs are directly related to the production of green hydrogen per unit of volume or energy. Included are the costs of energy, water, chemical inputs, and other costs related to electrolysis.

Both demand and production volume are based on the study published in the document *Hoja de Ruta del Hidrógeno en Colombia* [1]. In this study, a production cost of 1.7 USD/kg H₂ is established for 2030. For 2030, a price of 2.2 USD/kg is projected, for 2040 1.8 USD/kg and for 2050 1.5 USD/kg.

Based on the above, we estimate the income produced by the sale of hydrogen as value of 2 USD/kg, which gives us a value of 2 MUSD/kTon. A demand of 150 kTon per year is estimated, which leads us to an estimated value of 300 MUSD per year.

Other income generated by government incentives for contributing to the reduction of emissions is also considered.

Table 1 shows the estimated costs for the hydrogen production project.

Table 1.

Costing project

Item	Quantity	Unit cost	Total cost	Unit	Periodicity	Reference
Turbine Vestas V236 15 MW	117	\$ 13,2	\$ 1.544,4	MUSD	Initial investment	Vestas V236-15-0
Turbine maintenance	1	\$ 48,0	\$ 5,6	MUSD/year	Annual	Wind turbine cost
Wiring	1762	\$ 0,2	\$ 325,3	MUSD	Initial investment	Vestas-v236-15-0
Wiring installation	1762	\$ 0,0	\$ 54,2	MUSD	Initial investment	Vestas-v236-15-0
Electrolyzers	11	\$ 48,0	\$ 527,5	MUSD	Initial investment	Water electrolysis systems
Licenses			\$ 1,0	MUSD	Initial investment	
Turbine foundation	117	\$ 3,0	\$ 351,0	MUSD	Initial investment	Vestas-v236-15-0
Land purchase	250088	\$ 133,3	\$ 33,3	MUSD	Initial investment	
Others initial investments			\$ 851,0	MUSD	Initial investment	

The total initial investment is \$3.687,7 MUSD, the annual operative costs are \$6,6 MUSD and hydrogen annual sales are \$300 MUSD. Table 2

Table 2

Summary Cost and Investment, MUSD

Summary	
Initial investment	\$ 3.687,7
Hydrogen annual sales	\$ 300,0
Operative costs	\$ 6,6

- **Cash flow analysis:**

Perform a detailed analysis of the cash flow throughout the useful life of the project. This involves calculating annual revenues and costs and determining when the project is expected to break even and generate net profits. Appropriate discount rate to calculate the net present value (NPV) of the project. This rate reflects the opportunity cost of the capital invested and helps evaluate whether the project is financially attractive. The time it will take to recover the initial investment through the cash flows generated by the project.

Unforeseen events and financial risks associated with the project are considered, as well as the long-term financial impact, including asset depreciation, and long-term projections for the demand for green hydrogen.

Figure 18 Cash flow

Figure 18 shows the cash flow of the project over 30 years. With this, a Net Present Value of 350.64 million dollars and an Internal Rate of Return of 6.87% is determined.

The above shows that the project is economically viable.

Conclusions and future works

EDWIN

Green hydrogen has been identified as a sustainable and profitable way to produce energy.

A renewable source such as wind energy is ideal to move hydrogen production, there are many technical, logistical and economic challenges such as:

- Choosing a suitable location
- Selecting the appropriate electrolysis method.

- Determining the potential of wind energy based on the production capacity required to satisfy market demand.
- Storage and transportation.
- Infrastructure and electrical network design.
- Installation, operation and maintenance costs.
- Environmental regulations.
- Cultural changes involved.

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